

22DIT01 - ViDiT

Report on the open access software repository including the implementation of the methods and FAIR data sets developed for the uncertainty evaluation of virtual experiments and digital twins

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Deliverable Cover Sheet

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1 General comments

This report contains a detailed description of the open access software repository, references to the individual implementations and the data provided in the 22DIT01 project ViDiT “Trustworthy virtual experiments and digital twins”. The report begins in this section with a general overview of the repository and its accessibility. In Section 2, the software for uncertainty evaluation involving virtual experiments (VEs) is discussed and in Section 3, the software for uncertainty evaluation involving digital twins (DTs) is presented.

1.1 Availability and access

The actual open source software repository is available at PTB’s Gitlab server https://gitlab1.ptb.de/vidit-group/ViDiT_Software and can be downloaded as a whole, including all required datasets, from the following Zenodo community <https://zenodo.org/communities/vidit/>.

In the following sections, it is assumed that the whole repository has been downloaded, including all datasets.

1.2 Directory structure

The software is structured according to their interpretation as a virtual experiment (VE), which were treated in Work package (WP) one, or as a digital twin (DT), discussed in WP2, respectively. Subsequently, each application and use-case is represented by its own directory.

Figure 1. Overview of directory structure of ViDiT software repository available at [1].

1.3 Licence

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This software is licensed under the BSD-like license:

Redistribution and use in source and binary forms, with or without modification, are permitted provided that the following conditions are met:

1. Redistributions of source code must retain the above copyright notice, this list of conditions and the following disclaimer.
2. Redistributions in binary form must reproduce the above copyright notice, this list of conditions and the following disclaimer in the documentation and/or other materials provided with the distribution.

1.4 Disclaimer

This software was developed in the European Partnership project ViDiT. The software is provided “as is”, without warranty of any kind, express or implied, including but not limited to the warranties of merchantability, fitness for a particular purpose and noninfringement. In no event shall the authors, the consortium or partners of ViDiT, EURAMET, or the copyright holders be liable for any claim, damages or other liability, whether in an action of contract, tort or otherwise, arising from, out of or in connection with the software or the use or other dealings in the software.

2 Software for uncertainty evaluation using virtual experiments

The software repository and this section of the report is aligned with the applications considered in the project that involve virtual experiments, which were discussed in WP1: The Tilted-Wave interferometer (TWI), the Coordinate Measuring Machine (CMM) and the flow-meter measurements (FLOW).

2.1 Uncertainty evaluation for the tilted-wave interferometer

In this implementation, a benchmark scenario is developed that applies the concepts of a simplified version of a tilted-wave interferometer (TWI) in a simple and numerically efficient way to define a VE. For that, a linearization of the TWI is considered that has been generated from analytical and numerical derivatives of the actual TWI simulation model. The combination of this linear simulation (or forward) model with a simple additive homoscedastic Gaussian noise assumption, provides the virtual experiment under consideration for this task. Subsequently, the uncertainty estimation methods, which were developed in A1.1.1 of this project, are implemented and applied for this specific virtual experiment and two different measurement models. Several cases are distinguished that consider different uncertainties of the selected input parameters. You will find further explanations in the code (MATLAB® Live-Script). The goal of this software is to implement and compare several methods for uncertainty evaluation of a linearized VE in conjunction with measurement data. Note that the results are not representative of the actual TWI and may differ significantly from uncertainties obtained in real experiments.

Location and access

The implementations for uncertainty evaluation methods that were developed for and applied to the simplified TWI application can be found in the software repository at the following path

`vidit/WP1/Benchmark/TWI`

Programming language and requirements

The software is implemented in MATLAB® and was tested using version R2024b. The software requires no additional toolboxes, however, for parallel computation of some of the involved Monte Carlo simulations, the *MATLAB® Parallel computing toolbox* can be used.

FAIR dataset

The linearization of the TWI is developed for a specific scenario and was extracted from the actual and much more complex VE used in practice [2], which is implemented using SimOptDevice [3]. The linearization must be stored in form of a Jacobian matrix for the software to run. For this, the directory

```
vidit/WP1/Benchmark/TWI/DATA
```

is already included in the full repository. When cloning the Gitlab repository, this DATA directory must be included by the user. An in-depth description of the DATA that represents the numerical model for the linearized TWI can be found in the *DATA* directory, which also includes meta-data to ensure that the data is FAIR. In particular, the **.mat* files in the *DATA* directory contain matrices and data structures that define the linearization of the forward model of the TWI for a specific choice of operation. These datasets can be exchanged for alternative linear models and is interoperable with the provided MATLAB® source code.

Content and short description

Please refer to the *README* file first, available at

```
vidit/WP1/Benchmark/TWI/DATA/README.md
```

in the full Zenodo repository.

The actual implementations can be found in the MATLAB® live scripts

- *run_fwd_ve.mlx*
- *run_ncy_sota.mlx*
- *run_ncy_mcve.mlx*

that can be found in the folder

```
vidit/WP1/Benchmark/TWI/
```

The first live script *run_fwd_ve.mlx* loads the VE from the dataset and generates virtual data from the linearized VE to use in the following data analysis. The second live script *run_ncy_sota.mlx* implements several state-of-the-art methods for uncertainty evaluation and discusses their usage for a linear model, motivated by the linearized TWI use-case. The final live script *run_ncy_mcve.mlx* implements the newly developed MCVE approach [4] [5], which applies a JCGM 101- compliant uncertainty evaluation that relies solely on evaluations of the VE. A collection of helper functions that provide functionality of loading and using the linearized VE, operating with 2D Zernike polynomials, plotting, and many more, can be found in the directory

```
vidit/WP1/Benchmark/TWI/HELPERS
```

2.2 Uncertainty evaluation for the coordinate measuring machine

The goal of the coordinate measurement machine (CMM) benchmark scenario is to compare different uncertainty evaluation methods that use a virtual CMM. The software therefore implements the different uncertainty evaluation methods described in chapters 3 and 5 of D1. The benchmark scenario can be found at

[vidit/WP1/Benchmark/CMM](#)

Note that the synthetic data is generated during run-time, so no input data is required to run the CMM benchmark scenario. However, the functionality does exist to export the settings, generated synthetic data and output. This way, the CMM benchmark scenario results can easily be reused.

Programming language and requirements

The software is implemented in Python 3.10.11 and requires the following libraries (which can also be found in the file *requirements.txt*)

- numpy: 1.23.3
- pandas: 1.5.0
- scipy: 1.12.0
- matplotlib: 3.6.0
- emcee: 3.1.4
- openpyxl: 3.1.2

Content and short description

Please refer to the *README* file first, available at

[vidit/WP1/Benchmark/CMM/README.md](#)

The CMM benchmark scenario can be used by running the file *example_use_case.py*. In this script, one can adjust which uncertainty evaluation methods are calculated, as well as which output is generated (and where the output is stored, if at all). In addition, the settings of the virtual CMM can be adjusted in *default_settings_CMM_benchmark.json*. This includes the mean and uncertainty of the measurands and error sources, as well as other settings regarding the measured objects (i.e. number of measured data points, form imperfections, etc.). More information regarding the different settings that can be defined by the user is available in the CMM benchmark documentation page, found at

[vidit/WP1/Benchmark/CMM/Documentation/index.html](#)

2.3 Uncertainty evaluation for the flow-meter measurements

The objective of the flow meter benchmark scenario (FLOW) is to enable a comparative analysis and evaluation of various uncertainty evaluation methods applied to a virtual flow meter. The software has been developed to implement the uncertainty evaluation framework as described in the publication “A Novel

Framework for Uncertainty Evaluation Applied to a Virtual Flow Meter” (Measurement Science and Technology, DOI: 10.1088/1361-6501/adea0e) and can be found at

WP1/Benchmark/FLOW

This benchmark enables the assessment of the following methods, which are described in more detail in D1:

Method	Description
LPU-DA	Law of Propagation of Uncertainty using the Data Analysis (DA)
LPU-VEDA	Law of Propagation of Uncertainty using a Virtual Experiment-Data Analysis (VE-DA) combination
PoD-DA	Propagation of Distributions applied to DA
PoD-VEDA	Propagation of Distributions applied to VE, followed by DA

In the considered benchmark scenario, the methods use synthetic measurement data derived from a surrogate model. The surrogate model originates from “A virtual flow meter downstream of various elbow configurations” (Metrologia, DOI: 10.1088/1681-7575/ace7d6) and is available through the **FAIR dataset**, which is stored in the `gui_data/` directory.

The baseline case used for all calculations is predefined directly in the main script (`main.py`) and can be modified by the user if desired. No external input data is required to run the FLOW benchmark scenario as all parameters are defined internally, and synthetic data is generated at runtime. However, the results and settings can be exported for reproducibility and re-use.

Programming language and requirements

The software is implemented in Python 3.12 and requires the following main libraries:

- numpy
- pandas
- scipy
- matplotlib
- emcee
- openpyxl

These packages provide the necessary functionality for uncertainty propagation, data handling, statistical analysis and visualisation.

Content and usage

Please refer to the `README` file for a detailed description of the repository structure and theoretical background at

WP1/Benchmark/FLOW/README.md

The FLOW benchmark scenario can be executed by running:

```
python main.py
```

Within this script, the user can:

- select which uncertainty evaluation methods to run (or all at once),
- adjust input quantities and their uncertainties,
- modify parameters of the flow meter setup (e.g., Reynolds number, pipe diameter, curvature radius, etc.),
- define where and how results should be stored.

The script automatically loads the **FAIR Dataset** based surrogate model from the *gui_data/* directory. The computed results are written as *.txt* files to the *results/* folder.

Documentation and configuration

More information about the structure, model functions and mathematical details can be found in “A Novel Framework for Uncertainty Evaluation Applied to a Virtual Flow Meter” (*Measurement Science and Technology*, DOI: 10.1088/1361-6501/adea0e) and within the Gitlab documentation and in the source files. Source files contain:

- *model_functions.py*: defines forward and backward models for flow computations.
- *lpu_da.py*, *lpu_veda.py*, *pod_da.py*, *pod_veda.py*: contain the different uncertainty evaluation methods.
- *main.py*: defines the baseline case and executes the selected method(s).

FAIR dataset

The surrogate model used for the FLOW benchmark scenario is based on a numerical model representing the fluid dynamic behaviour downstream of different elbow configurations / disturbances. This model forms the basis of the uncertainty assessment framework and complies with the FAIR data principles. The surrogate model data are included in the directory: *gui_data/*

This directory contains the precomputed data sets that make up the FAIR Dataset and are taken from the publication “A virtual flow meter downstream of various elbow configurations” (*Metrologia*, DOI: 10.1088/1681-7575/ace7d6).

The data represent a VE setup, which allows synthetic flow profiles to be generated at runtime without the need for experimental input data.

The *gui_data/* directory contains the following main components

- *FLOW_class_AW* - Surrogate model metadata and configuration.
- *FLOW_Meters/* - numerical data for various flow meter geometries.
- *FLOW_Profiles/* - simulated velocity and pressure field profiles for different elbow configurations.

When cloning the GitLab or GitHub repository, this directory must be included to ensure that the virtual FLOW model works correctly. The files define the surrogate model used by all uncertainty evaluation methods (LPU-DA, LPU-VEDA, PoD-DA, PoD-VEDA) implemented in the software.

The FAIR dataset can be exchanged with alternative surrogate models, provided they follow the same structural conventions. This interoperability allows users to apply the same uncertainty assessment framework to other flow configurations or measurement setups, supporting reproducibility and method benchmarking.

3 Software for uncertainty evaluation using digital twins

The software repository contains demos of traceable and trustworthy digital twins with uncertainty evaluation for different applications.

3.1 Uncertainty evaluation for nanoindentation

This code contains functionality for the training and statistical testing of a nanoindentation testing machine Digital Twin (DT) for a specific combination of sample and indenter.

The DT is trained based on experimental measurements under nominal working conditions. Uncertainty estimation methods are applied to the mechanical characterization of the sample to create a virtual representation of the system under control.

Batches of experimental measurements can be tested through statistical tests to control the shape of the indentation curves and surface mechanical properties.

This code implements the methodology described in Section 3 of Deliverable D2 [6].

Location and access

The implementations for uncertainty evaluation methods that were developed for and apply to the TWI application can be found in the software repository at the following path

```
vidit/WP2/Nanoindentation
```

Programming language and requirements

The code is written in Python 3.11.9, using the additional packages listed below. For more information, please refer to the *README* file and the *requirements* file.

- numpy: 1.26.4
- matplotlib: 3.8.4
- scipy: 1.13.1
- tqdm: 4.66.4
- tabulate: 0.9.0

FAIR dataset

The DT of the nanoindentation is based on experimental data. FAIR dataset are provided at

```
vidit/WP2/Nanoindentation/Datasets
```

The folder contains datasets collected at POLITO with an Anton Paar NHT3 platform and at UNIPD with a Nanomechanics nanoindentation machine. Data are collected on SiO₂ and on W, ranging on in-control conditions (“Si_BBI-68_Nuove”, “Train_W”, “Test_W”, “Si_refs”) and with out-of-control conditions, e.g. induced by worn out indenter (“test_BC-A10”), by turned off air conditioning (“test_FS_air_conditioning_problems”), and with heated (“test_UNIPD_hot”) or cooled samples (“test_UNIPD_cold”).

The datasets also contains examples of the results of the applications of the DT to such datasets at:

vidit/WP2/Nanoindentation/Output

The DT model can also be applied to generate synthetic datasets. The code for synthetic data generation is available at

vidit/WP2/Nanoindentation/code/Artificial_Dataset.py

Content and short description

Please refer to the *README* file first, available at

vidit/WP2/Nanoindentation/code/README.md

Two main files are provided for the training of the DT and its use in statistical testing experimental curves, respectively.

vidit/WP2/Nanoindentation/code/DT_Training.py
vidit/WP2/Nanoindentation/code/DT_Test.py

- **DT_Training.py**: training of the DT based on the experimental curves provided in the specified `train_folder`. The code creates and saves the DT model of the system, a text log with mechanical properties and their uncertainty and graphical plots if requested by the user in the `# INPUTS` section
- **DT_Test.py**: experimental curves in the `test_folder` are tested against the DT model with 12 statistical tests to control the shape of the indentation curve, the thermal drift during the experiment and mechanical properties. Each rejected text is recorded in a text log file, listing the specific indentation not under control, type I error probability α , test p -value and type II error probability β .

Machine and sample specific `# INPUTS` and `# DEFINITIONS` (indenter area function parameters, machine frame compliance, indenter Young's Modulus, indenter and sample Poisson's ratio, ...) need to be defined in the upper parts of each file. Additional documentation regarding each variable is provided within the code. Details on the software usage are provided in Section 3.1 of Deliverable D4 [7].

3.2 Uncertainty evaluation for the reference rotary table (angle measurement)

Location and access

The implementation developed for the uncertainty evaluation of the reference rotary table (LNE) can be found in the ViDiT software repository at:

vidit/WP2/Virtual reference table/

This directory contains the MATLAB implementation of the virtual rotary table (VE) used for angular metrology studies and uncertainty evaluation.

The main script is:

Virtual rotary table-MATLAB generator of the virtual rotary table experiment.

An optional resource file containing measured mechanical wobble profiles is used automatically if available:

resources/wobble.csv

The outputs of the simulation (FAIR-compliant CSVs) are written to:

data/processed/

and are described in the associated metadata file:

```
metadata/rotary_ve24.yaml
```

Programming language and requirements

The software is implemented in MATLAB® (tested with version R2024b).

No toolbox is required; the Parallel Computing Toolbox is optional for batch processing.

Typical execution time for a full simulation (1000 experiments, 24 faces) is a few seconds, producing less than 2 MB of CSV data.

The script automatically loads the optional resources/wobble.csv file if present.

The outputs are encoded in UTF-8 CSV format and can be analysed directly in MATLAB or Python.

FAIR dataset

The dataset generated by the virtual rotary table is compliant with FAIR principles.

Findable: Metadata and structured directory under

```
vidit/WP2/Reference rotary table/Virtual rotary table/metadata/rotary_ve24.yaml.
```

Accessible: All files (data, code, metadata) are included in the public Zenodo repository at the project's final release.

Interoperable: CSV format with SI units (angles in degrees, temperature in °C).

Reusable: CC-BY-4.0 license for data, BSD-3-Clause for code.

Main outputs (CSV):

```
ve24_theta_true_deg_24x15deg.csv          # nominal polygon face angles (deg)
ve24_theta_meas_deg_24x15deg.csv         # simulated measured angles (deg)
ve24_E_ecc_deg.csv                       # eccentricity contribution
ve24_E_tilt_deg.csv                      # tilt contribution
ve24_E_ax_deg.csv                        # axial component
ve24_E_th_deg.csv                        # global thermal drift
ve24_E_gradT_deg.csv                    # thermal gradient
ve24_E_DC_turn_deg.csv                  # intra-turn DC bias
ve24_E_dyn_deg.csv                      # dynamic vibration term
ve24_E_face_bias_deg.csv                # face bias
ve24_E_scale_off_deg.csv                # scale and offset error
ve24_summary_rms_deg.csv                # per-experiment RMS summary
```

Metadata (excerpt):

```
dataset_id:          vidit-rotary-ve24-2025-10
title:               "Virtual Rotary Table - LNE static 24-face VE"
creators:            ["Rim Bennoune (LNE/ENS Paris-Saclay)", "Hichem Nouira (LNE)"]
instrument:          "LNE reference rotary table"
version:             0.1.0
license:             CC-BY-4.0
```

Checksums can be generated using:

```
find data/processed -type f -name 've24_*.csv' -exec sha256sum {} \; > checksums.txt
```

Content and short description

This Virtual Experiment (VE) simulates a 24-face polygon under static conditions ($\omega \approx 0$). It reproduces the measurement behaviour of the LNE reference rotary table, including realistic sources of error, to support model validation and uncertainty evaluation of a future Digital Twin.

The main effects implemented are:

Geometric SDT components: eccentricity (Tx, Ty), tilt (Rx, Ry), optional axial (Tz).

Thermal behaviour: global drift ($\Delta\theta T = \alpha \cdot \Delta T$) with AR(1) thermal dynamics and a small gradient term $A_{gradT} \cdot \cos(\theta - \phi T)$.

Encoder effects: interpolation ripple ($m = 8-32$), INL harmonics ($h = 4-12$) for both fixed and mobile encoders.

Noise and bias: mixture of Gaussian/Laplace noise, turn-level bias (EDC_turn), optional wobble input.

Readout errors: scale (± 50 ppm), offset (~ 0.01 arcsec std), rare index jitter (± 1 step), optional one-step latency.

Dynamics: small vibration and angular-rate effects (disabled by default for static runs).

The outputs enable:

Monte Carlo uncertainty evaluation (GUM-MC) using the synthetic data,

Estimator benchmarking (EKF/PF), and

Sensitivity analysis of geometric, thermal, and dynamic contributions.

Dataset ID: vidit-rotary-ve24-2025-10, Version 0.1.0 (October 2025)
 Creators: Rim Bennoune (LNE / ENS Paris-Saclay), Hichem Nourira (LNE)

3.3 Uncertainty evaluation for optical machine-vision measurement

Within the framework of the ViDiT project (Trustworthy virtual experiments and digital twins in metrology), a conceptual digital twin demonstrator for optical machine-vision measurement has been developed.

The tool aims to estimate measurement uncertainty in geometrical feature inspection (e.g., planes and spheres) by virtually representing the main elements of a vision-based measurement system: the sensor, calibration setup, robot positioning, and environmental configuration.

Although the demonstrator does not implement a fully coupled real–virtual system, it provides a functional digital representation of the measurement process, enabling users to study the influence of system parameters and sources of error on the resulting uncertainty.

In this sense, the software serves as a simplified but pedagogically valuable digital twin environment for uncertainty evaluation and supports the ViDiT objective of promoting reliable, traceable, and explainable digital metrology practices.

Location and access

The software implementation developed by IDEKO for uncertainty evaluation in optical vision systems is available in the internal ViDiT software repository under the folder:

/ViDiT/WP2/DT Robotic Scanning

Detailed documentation, and the XML configuration file used by the application are included in the same directory.

Programming language and requirements

The application is developed in Python 3.8, using the following packages:

- tkinter - for the graphical user interface
- Pillow – for image and icon management

To install dependencies:

```
pip install Pillow
pip install tkinter
```

Ensure that the following files are located in the same directory as the main script:

- data.xml – XML configuration file containing parameter sets for robot, calibration, and sensor options
- /logos/ – folder including logo1.png and custom_icon.ico

FAIR dataset

To ensure reproducibility and traceability, an example dataset is provided, containing sample XML configurations for:

- Different **robot setups** and their positioning uncertainty,
- **Calibration factors** and alignment parameters, and
- **Optical sensor models** with characteristic field-of-view and point uncertainty values.

These datasets allow users to replicate the example cases demonstrated in Section 3.3 of Deliverable D4 [7] and to validate their own parameter configurations.

Content and short description

The software provides a **graphical user interface (GUI)** that allows the user to select and configure measurement parameters through dropdown menus and numeric fields. It calculates the combined measurement uncertainty based on analytical models that take into account the main error sources of an optical measurement setup.

Main scripts:

- **Optical_DT_GUI.py** – Main script that launches the graphical interface. Users can select the sensor, robot, and calibration options from dropdown menus, and visualize the resulting uncertainty.
- **data.xml** – Contains configuration parameters for the available robots, calibrations, and sensors. Each entry includes attributes such as number of points, field of view, and base uncertainty.
- **logos/** – Folder containing graphical resources used in the GUI.

Upon execution, the interface displays input menus, numerical boxes, and a calculation button. The computed uncertainty value is shown directly in the GUI and can be exported as a text file.

3.4 Uncertainty evaluation for electrical measurements

3.4.1 High voltage

Content and short description

For the high voltage measurements application, a DT has been developed. With the software of this DT it is possible to perform the electrical calculations and estimations of the sheath currents and voltages in insulated

power lines. Inside this software, it is included the software for the uncertainty estimation of the results obtained with the DT. In this section, all the software, data and scripts provided in the repository are described. With all these contributions, the user can evaluate the functioning of the program.

An executable of the software is included in:

[vidit/WP2/ High Voltage Measurements/SPACS_demo.zip](#)

This executable contains a demo version of the whole DT software. As the uncertainty evaluation has been implemented inside the DT software, it is not possible to provide a separate program for the uncertainty evaluation. Instead, Monte Carlo method can be applied from within the user interface of the DT. Nevertheless, the code related to the uncertainty evaluation applying the Monte Carlo method execution, is provided in:

[vidit/WP2/ High Voltage Measurements/Monte Carlo/MC_code_extract.m](#)

The results obtained with the Monte Carlo method are automatically plotted. Along with the previous plots, two *.mat files containing all the data generated by the Monte Carlo execution are saved when the method is run. Nevertheless, a script to generate more user-friendly plots using the output generated by the Monte Carlo method (and saved in the mentioned *.mat files) is given in:

[vidit/WP2//High Voltage Measurements/Monte Carlo/MC_result_analysis.mlx](#)

Detailed instructions on how to use the demo version of the DT and the scripts for visualizing the results of the uncertainty evaluation are given in Section 3.5.1 of Deliverable D4 [7].

FAIR dataset

For the high voltage application, the provided software and data on the FAIR repository is intended to provide the user with sufficient data to test the demo software provided.

For the high voltage measurements application, the software and data provided in the FAIR repository are intended to provide the user with sufficient data for the execution of the uncertainty evaluation method and also for the evaluation of the demo software provided. All the necessary code for the uncertainty evaluation is included in the DT software and can be used from within its graphical user interface.

Using the data gathered by the sensors of a certain power line, two synthetic datasets can be built.

- Instant dataset: it is intended to be used for the uncertainty evaluation when the DT software is run in its static version (when only certain individual instants of time are considered).
- 24h curves dataset: it is intended to be used for the uncertainty evaluation when the DT software is run in its dynamic version (considering a certain time span).

The data given the two indicated purposes can be found in:

[vidit/WP2/High Voltage Measurements/Data/Test_data_HVAC.csv](#)

This data includes:

- Temperature readings in the outer layer of the cable in certain joints.

- Voltage in each phase.
- Current through the active conductors at both power line endings.
- Current through the sheaths in both power line endings.
- Differential current through the sheaths in cable joints.
- Calculated sheath currents for each mayor section.
- Calculated active, reactive and apparent power.

For the complex variables, the values are stored as real and imaginary part.

Some of this data can be used as input for performing the dynamical analysis and the uncertainty evaluation in the demo version of the DT. Further details on how to enter this data and on how to perform the uncertainty evaluation on the software are given on the user manual (D4). On the other hand, for a static analysis of the power line in the demo software, all the data can be entered manually by the user, so no files are required.

All the scripts used to generate the two synthetic datasets can be found in the following folder:

`vidit/WP2/High Voltage Measurements/Scripts for synthetic data generation`

The scripts available in the previous folder are:

1. Curve viewer: this script allows to plot the variables of interest to choose the days desired to use as entry for the interpolation of 24h-curves. It uses as entry the given test data file.
2. Curve treatment: this script allows to combine similar curves (by calculating the mean). It also allows to filter the curves, smoothing them, by performing the moving average. This script generates a *.mat file as output. It uses as entry the given test data file.
3. Curve interpolation: this script performs the interpolation between a given dataset of original curves. It uses as entry a folder containing multiple *.mat files generated by the curve treatment script.
4. Instant dataset active power: this script is provided with as many original data as possible to build a dataset that contains samples for a specified range of values of power and temperature. The script searches within the original data as many temperature-active power pairs as possible that meet the requirements established. Then, for the missing pairs, interpolation is used to complete them.
5. Instant dataset apparent power: its aim is the same as the one of the script number 4, but it uses the apparent power as the input variable for the interpolation. Again, this script is provided with as many original data as possible to build a dataset that contains samples for a specified range of values of power and temperature. The script searches within the original data as many temperature-apparent power pairs as possible that meet the requirements established. Then, for the missing pairs, interpolation is used to complete them.

To summarize the function of each of the previous scripts, and to facilitate their use, the following flow chart is given, where the workflow to expand the original dataset of 24h curves is shown.

Regarding the instants dataset, it is only necessary to execute either the instant dataset for active power interpolation script (A04) or the instant dataset for apparent power interpolation script (A05).

Note that the original data file is the file provided on the FAIR dataset. It can be used to generate the two datasets proposed. In real scenarios, for the instant dataset it is recommended that a file with as many data as possible is used. In this way, the script can select as many registers as possible from the original data, reducing the need for interpolation, which improves the reliability of the dataset.

For the use of these scripts, the user must only fill the required variables (which are used to specify the input files and other configurations), following the instructions given in the code comments.

NOMENCLATURE SUMMARY

To facilitate the use of the scripts and the data provided, the nomenclature used with them is explained.

The data given is from a power line which endings are “SubA” and “SubB” (which stands for substations A and B respectively), which is composed of 15 sections, all with the sheath connected in cross-bonding. There are 4 intermediate grounded joints (which are named, starting from SubA, CE3, CE6, CE9 and CE12). In CE3, CE6 and CE9 joints there are sensor readings available.

For the currents, the name of each variable is structured in the following way:

For current readings:

For the voltage, the location is substituted by “Tensi_n”, as it is only measured in one point of the power line.

As for the temperatures, the nomenclature is as follows:

For temperature readings:

Except for the ambient temperature, which is only measured at CE3, and it is stored as “Temp_Nvz_CE3_Tamb”.

Other variables have been calculated using the previous data as a starting point. This include the power readings and the current through each sheath for each section. The nomenclature is summarized in the following chart.

For sheath currents:

For power:

For testing the estimation of the uncertainty in dynamic mode, the following file is given:

```
vidit/WP2/High Voltage Measurements/Data/CurvaCarga60min.txt
```

This file can be generated by the user from any of the given load curves of the dataset or from any of the synthetic curves generated by the user. This file is provided only as an example, to facilitate the use of the demo version without having to process any data.

3.4.2 Internal arc test

The software goal is to simulate internal arc faults in medium-voltage switchgear. In this simulation, two cases are developed that applies the concepts of simplified analytical modelling of arc-induced overpressure inside a switchgear and, if present, through a duct into the surrounding compartment. The simulation framework combines a set of analytical formulations (described in *D2, Section 6.2*) with user-defined geometrical, electrical, and thermodynamic input parameters.

To account for uncertainties, the software allows the user to specify probability distributions for critical input parameters such as ignition voltage and current, compartment volume, or discharge coefficients. These distributions are then propagated through the simulation model using a Monte Carlo approach, enabling the evaluation of resulting uncertainties in the pressure profiles. Several cases can be distinguished depending on the presence or absence of a duct, and on whether single- or three-phase arc faults are considered.

The goal of this software is therefore not only to simulate a single deterministic scenario, but also to implement and compare uncertainty propagation methods for internal arc simulations, providing a reliable framework for sensitivity analysis and robustness evaluation of different switchgear configurations in accordance with several standards.

The code is:

[WP2/Internal Arc Test DT/IATOS.py](#)

This script contains the last version of the software. The uncertainty evaluation could be implemented inside the software, and it is possible to provide a simulation without uncertainty evaluation. Instead, the Monte Carlo method can be applied without the user interface. The code related to the uncertainty evaluation applying the Monte Carlo method execution, is provided in:

[WP2/Internal Arc Test DT/arco_interno_analitico.py](#)

Detailed instructions on how to use the software for visualizing the results of the uncertainty evaluation are given in Section 3.5.2 of Deliverable D4 [7]. A brief description of is given in the README file located in

[WP2/Internal Arc Test DT/README.m d](#)

To run the software, make sure you have Python 3, Tkinter, NumPy, and Matplotlib installed. Open a CMD terminal in the same directory as IATOS.py and run it using the Python interpreter. The program should start in a new window.

Two reference test cases are provided in the data linked below

[WP2/Internal Arc Test DT/data/cases.xlsx](#)

The dataset contains all the necessary configuration input parameters to reproduce the benchmark simulations and verify the performance of the software, with and without duct.

3.4.3 Quantum voltage standard

The goal of the quantum voltage standard DT software is to develop a model of the physical system that makes predictions of its behavior with uncertainty quantification. The code prepares the data for dataset creation, trains a sequence-to-sequence mixture density network (the model of the digital twin), and then makes predictions with uncertainty quantification using GUM Monte Carlo for input uncertainty propagation and Monte Carlo dropout for the model's uncertainty. It produces multi-step forecasts with decomposed uncertainty (aleatoric, epistemic, and input-induced). Finally, it plots the results comparing predictions with test data. The code implements the methodology depicted in Section 6.3 of Deliverable D2 [6].

The software can be found at:

[vidit/WP2/Quantum Voltage Standard DT](#)

The code is programmed in Python, using the additional packages listed below. For more information, please refer to the README file and the requirements file.

Prerequisites:

- Python 3.9+ recommended
- pip

- GPU recommended for training but CPU will work (training and Monte Carlo sampling may be slow on CPU)
- Disk: able to store data/ outputs (model + npz files)

Required Python packages:

- `numpy>=1.21.0`
- `tensorflow>=2.10.0`
- `keras>=2.10.0`
- `scikit-learn>=1.1.0`
- `matplotlib>=3.5.0`
- `joblib>=1.1.0`

The FAIR dataset (`DC_1V_100000pts_25µsAper_20kSs.txt`) contains the raw voltage values of a DC measurement of 1 V, performed with TÜBITAK UME PJVS system. The software processes this data to match the model inputs. Dataset and all the files generated by the code are in

`vidit/WP2/Quantum Voltage Standard DT/data`

Software is divided into three applications:

- Data preparation (`prepare_data.py`): takes the raw voltage from the measurements and processes this time-series data to build sequence-to-sequence sets, splits them into training/validation/test datasets, and scales the data so it's ready to use to train the model. It saves the scalers and datasets for future use.
- Model training (`train_model.py`): loads the scaled training/validation datasets, builds and trains the Mixture Density Network model (with MC-Dropout for epistemic uncertainty), then saves the trained model and its parameters.
- Uncertainty calculation (`calc_uncertainty.py`): loads the trained model, calculates predictive mean and decomposed uncertainty (aleatoric, epistemic, input-induced) using GUM Monte Carlo input propagation with MC-Dropout. It saves the results and parameters/metrics and plots an example of a single prediction with measurement uncertainty.

These applications are in

`vidit/WP2/Quantum Voltage Standard DT/scripts`

A detailed explanation of how the code works and how to run it can be found in the README.md file, located in

`vidit/WP2/Quantum Voltage Standard DT/README.md`

4 References

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